

Towards Optimizing Reinforcement Learning Workload Placement at the Cloud-Edge Continuum in 6G Networks: A Scaled RL Framework

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Abstract—With the increasing deployment of Reinforcement Learning (RL) for network optimization at the edge of wireless networks, the RL workload emerges as a significant challenge. While the placement of general Machine Learning workloads across the cloud–edge continuum has been widely studied, existing solutions typically exclude RL techniques due to their distinct structure and operational requirements. In this work, we propose a framework for RL workload placement in the cloud–edge continuum, enabling the scaling of RL actor processes across both domains. In this framework, agents that interact with the environment through simple feedback loops are deployed at the edge, while training and model storage are performed in the cloud, where sufficient computational resources are available. We implement and simulate a prototype of one scaled RL actor that performs Quality-of-Service-aware resource block assignment with separate threads for environment interaction, inference, buffering/sampling, and the learning process. Finally, we outline the open challenges of the proposed framework.

Index Terms—6G Networks, Cloud-Edge Continuum, Reinforcement Learning, Workload Placement

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background

Cloud computing builds on the promise of economies of scale, offering enhanced scalability and reliability through elastic resource provisioning. Scaling is achieved by instantiating multiple compute nodes and distributing workloads among them. This leads to the perception of infinite resource availability through horizontal scaling. However, achieving this illusion depends heavily on efficient load balancing, a fundamental challenge in distributed and cloud environments. The primary goal of load balancing is to allocate tasks across available servers to prevent bottlenecks and ensure system responsiveness. Without it, users may experience degraded Quality of Service (QoS), violations of Service Level Agreements (SLAs), data processing delays, and overall poor performance. As modern computing systems continue to scale, implementing effective load balancing becomes increasingly vital.

To support latency-sensitive services and enhance responsiveness, the edge cloud computing paradigm has emerged. It enables partial cloud services to be executed at the network edge, leveraging limited local compute resources. Edge

computing shifts computation and storage closer to end users, outside centralized data centers, reducing network latency and unlocking new application domains. While the majority of data is generated at the edge, most intensive processing is still handled in centralized cloud infrastructures. Therefore, orchestrating resources across the edge and cloud becomes crucial for ensuring optimal performance [1]–[5].

The cloud–edge continuum spans a range of compute environments, from powerful cloud data centers to lightweight edge devices such as Internet of Things (IoT) gateways, mobile phones, and micro data centers. Applications can dynamically partition and execute their logic across this continuum based on latency, energy, and availability requirements [5].

Traditional load balancing techniques, such as round-robin, least connections, and weighted round-robin, rely on fixed rules and static assumptions. Thus, they are not sufficient for modern network systems. Future networks must be agile, programmable, and load-efficient to counter challenges such as network congestion, high transmission costs, and unreliability. These methods are simple but often inadequate in dynamic cloud environments, where workloads fluctuate due to variable user demand, changing traffic patterns, and diverse application behaviors. Consequently, these static methods often result in suboptimal performance, server overload, increased response times, and inefficient use of resources. To overcome these limitations, Artificial Intelligence (AI), particularly machine learning (ML), has emerged as a promising tool for building intelligent, context-aware load balancing strategies. However, ML itself imposes computational demands on the infrastructure, necessitating careful management and load balancing of ML workloads as well [1], [2].

In this context, ML load balancing in the cloud–edge continuum refers to the dynamic allocation of machine learning tasks, including training, inference, and pre-processing, across the edge, fog, and cloud layers. The objective is to jointly optimize for latency (near-real-time response), energy efficiency, resource utilization (CPU, GPU, bandwidth), model accuracy, scalability, and resilience. This requires intelligent decisions about where (i.e., at what tier) each ML task should be executed. Related techniques include split com-

puting, model offloading and migration, federated learning optimization, Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC), Service Function Chaining (SFC), and distributed AI orchestration across emerging 6G, IoT [6], [7], and edge-enabled systems [5].

Among ML techniques, Reinforcement Learning (RL) has garnered significant attention due to its ability to learn optimal policies through continuous interaction with the environment and accumulation of experience. Its trial-and-error learning paradigm, in which agents adjust actions to maximize long-term rewards, makes RL particularly well-suited for the dynamic and uncertain nature of distributed computing systems. In recent years, various RL-based approaches have been proposed to solve optimization problems in edge and far-edge computing domains, including dynamic beamforming, adaptive modulation, and QoS-aware scheduling, etc. However, RL workflows are inherently composed of heterogeneous components, such as environment simulation, model inference, model training, and replay buffer management, each requiring different types and levels of computational resources. These requirements often exceed the capabilities of edge and far-edge nodes. Consequently, the problem of effectively distributing and placing RL workloads across the cloud–edge continuum remains largely underexplored, highlighting a critical gap in current research.

B. Related works

This section reviews existing research on load balancing and task offloading in the cloud–edge continuum, where RL has been widely adopted to improve scalability, adaptability, and autonomy. Several works employ decentralized or hybrid RL frameworks, such as those combining Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) with Multi-Agent RL (MARL), enabling local agents to optimize resources independently while maintaining global coordination in dynamic environments [8]. MARL has also been applied to Service Function Chain (SFC) placement, achieving notable improvements in balancing profit, latency, and resource utilization [9]. At the device level, actor–critic models support task offloading by maximizing Quality of Experience (QoE) under energy and latency constraints in 5G networks [10]. Beyond offloading, RL has been leveraged in Function-as-a-Service (FaaS) and Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) for auto-scaling and workload scheduling, where MARL agents dynamically balance compute loads to meet SLAs, reduce latency, and enhance throughput [11], [12]. In addition, Deep Q-Networks (DQN) have shown effectiveness for workload scheduling under high-load conditions, minimizing task failures and optimizing VM utilization [13] and service management in IoT networks [14]. Collectively, these studies highlight the versatility of RL in optimizing distributed systems, yet they often overlook the challenges of RL workload placement itself, particularly the large number of environment interactions and high computational demands required by RL algorithms.

C. Motivation and contribution

While we reviewed several RL-based load balancing approaches within the Edge–Cloud continuum, many other RL-driven optimization problems exist across intelligent wireless networks, particularly at the edge and far-edge layers. These tasks span a wide range of objectives, from radio resource management to QoS-aware service orchestration.

RL inherently comprises diverse components such as environment interaction, model inference, policy training, and replay buffer management, each with distinct computational demands [15]. Although the RL life-cycle typically requires resource availability similar to that of centralized cloud infrastructures, the agent must also maintain continuous interaction with its environment, often located at the network edge. As RL is increasingly adopted for time-sensitive optimizations across various tiers of the continuum, its computational demands pose a significant challenge. Despite its growing adoption, the problem of RL load placement (i.e., determining how and where to execute the different components of an RL agent within the cloud–edge continuum) remains largely unaddressed in current literature.

In this study, we:

- Present a system model employing Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) deployed across regional and edge cloud infrastructures.
- Propose a scaled RL actor framework that communicates with the environment at the edge while offloading computationally intensive components to the regional cloud.
- Implement the scaled actor using an enhanced version of the Deep Q-Learning (DQL) technique with LSTM-based Q-network.
- Discuss the practical challenges of scaling RL actors across the cloud–edge continuum and present future directions for developing scalable RL agents suited for edge–cloud environments.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

As illustrated in Fig. 1, we consider a three-tier architecture comprising edge, fog, and regional cloud levels within the network. These layers form a hierarchical structure in the distributed computing continuum, each offering distinct trade-offs between resource availability and latency. Edge nodes, located nearest to end devices (e.g., base stations, gateways), provide ultra-low latency but are constrained in terms of compute, memory, and storage capacity. Fog nodes, typically situated at aggregation points such as local data centers, serve as intermediate infrastructure with moderate resource availability and latency, enabling more complex processing tasks than edge nodes while preserving responsiveness. Regional clouds (or centralized data centers) offer abundant computational and storage resources but incur higher latency due to their physical distance from end users, making them ideal for large-scale or delay-tolerant workloads. Efficient orchestration across these three layers is essential to meet application, specific QoS requirements.

Fig. 1. The system model including the scaled RL actor placement

In our system model, we map the O-RAN architecture [16] onto the cloud–edge continuum: O-RAN Radio Units (O-RUs) are positioned at the edge site/cloud layer; O-RAN Distributed Units (O-DUs) and O-RAN Central Unit - User Plane (O-CU-UP) components are deployed at the fog layer; and O-RAN Central Unit - Control Plane (O-CU-CP), along with RAN Intelligent Controllers (RICs) are hosted in the regional cloud.

In the next section, we introduce the scaled RL agent placement in the cloud–edge continuum and provide a detailed review of its structure.

III. SCALED RL ARCHITECTURE

By closely analyzing the functionality of RL actors, it becomes clear that a crucial part of their behavior involves continuous interaction with the environment. This interaction loop, responsible for observing states, selecting actions, and receiving feedback, requires minimal computational resources. However, it must be executed in close proximity to the environment to satisfy real-time responsiveness constraints. In contrast, the other components of an RL actor, such as policy networks, neural network inference and training, replay buffer management, and other computational processes, demand significantly more resources.

Inspired by [15], [17], we decompose the RL actor into two distinct functional blocks: an Agent, which handles lightweight communication with the environment, and a Learner, which performs the computationally intensive tasks such as training, inference, and buffer processing. In our proposed framework, a lightweight agent is deployed across edge sites for each RL-based optimization. At the same time, a single learner resides in the regional cloud, where sufficient computational resources are available for training and model management.

As illustrated in Fig. 2, the learner encompasses the trained models, a shared replay buffer, and the inference pipeline. Meanwhile, the agent functions as a lightweight loop or process on the edge site, requiring negligible computational overhead.

To better understand the roles of the agents and the learner, we describe their operations below:

On the edge site/cloud: The agent is responsible for observing the environment and transmitting the collected observations, rewards, and episode termination flags to the learner. The agent also receives action outputs from the learner in response to these observations.

On the regional cloud: The learner receives sequences of observations, rewards, and termination signals. It stores the corresponding recurrent states, samples a batch of sequences, and adds them to the replay buffer (the training queue). It then samples these trajectories to prepare training batches for the agent.

As illustrated in Fig. 2, one learner can manage multiple agents on the edge, each corresponding to one RL-based optimization. While the environment for all the agents is the same, they have different observations and monitor their related instance of the environment. In order to support multiple agents seamlessly, we consider three different threads for the learner:

- **The Inference Thread :** This thread waits for observations from the actor thread. It passes these observations through the Q-network and returns a greedy action back to the actor. This thread performs no learning and shuts down gracefully when it receives a None signal.
- **The Pre-fetch Thread :** This thread monitors the Sequence Replay Buffer. Once a sufficient number of sequences are available, it samples a batch and forwards it to the (train) queue for consumption by the learner. Its primary role is to decouple data sampling from training, and it avoids busy waiting by sleeping briefly between checks.
- **The Learner Thread :** This thread continuously waits for batches in the queue. Upon receiving a batch, it trains the main Q-network using the loss computed with target values. The training relies on LSTM-based Q-value estimates over full sequences, with the loss calculated as mean squared error between predicted and target Q-values. Periodically, the target network is updated to match the weights of the main network.

In order to optimize the framework even further, When each agent waits for a response from the learner, it can interact with other environments instead of staying idle [15]. Thus, beyond scaling the RL workload, resource optimization can be achieved in two ways. First, by using a single agent (in its idle time) for either the same task (e.g., RB allocation) across multiple users or for different tasks that share a similar action space (e.g., selecting RBs or choosing the optimal modulation scheme), while training separate models using the same algorithm. Second, by leveraging the same computational resources on the learner side to run different algorithms, whether with discrete or continuous action spaces, across various edge optimization problems.

In the next section, the details of a simple version of the proposed approach are provided. In this implementation, one DQL actor with a simplified LSTM-based Q-network is scaled to an agent and a learner. This agent performs resource block allocation for different service types in the edge.

Fig. 2. The system model including the scaled RL actor placement

IV. SIMULATIONS, NUMERICAL RESULTS, AND OPEN CHALLENGES

While the proposed method is scaled and distributed through different locations, in this paper, we implement a scaled RL actor with a single agent using an improved version of DQL locally. However, the possible improvements and open challenges are going to be discussed later.

A. Simulation Setup

The scaled RL actor in our simulation operates using four threads: one dedicated to the agent and three supporting the learning pipeline, as detailed in Section III. The agent implements a simplified, single-instance variant of the R2D2 algorithm to assign resource blocks for different service types. While it retains the core components of R2D2, such as a recurrent Q-network based on LSTM, a target network for stable updates, a sequence-based replay buffer, off-policy training using TD targets, and thread-safe experience collection, it omits several advanced features. Specifically, the burn-in mechanism is not included, and only 1-step TD targets are used. Furthermore, the replay buffer employs uniform sampling instead of prioritized experience replay. The system also lacks distributed multi-agent actors, and the Q-network follows a standard architecture rather than the dueling network design.

The Q-network architecture begins with *TimeDistributed* dense layers featuring 64 *ReLU*-activated units to extract spatial features from the multi-user observations at each time step. A masking layer is incorporated to handle variable-length sequences by ignoring padded observations, ensuring the LSTM processes only valid network states. The core LSTM layer with 64 hidden units is configured with *return - sequences =*

True, enabling it to maintain and propagate hidden states across the observation sequence while outputting Q-value estimates at each step. The agent employs *epsilon - greedy* exploration during action selection, balancing exploitation of learned Q-values with random exploration to discover improved scheduling policies. Gradient clipping is applied during training to prevent exploding gradients common in recurrent architectures, and the target network is periodically updated to stabilize the learning process.

The environment is a custom OpenAI Gym environment designed to simulate RB allocation at the network edge or far edge, where a centralized scheduler assigns radio resources to users with heterogeneous service requirements. It models a wireless edge scenario with num_users and num_rbs , where each user is randomly assigned one of three QoS types: *eMBB* (enhanced Mobile Broadband), *URLLC* (Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communications), or *mMTC* (massive Machine Type Communications).

The observation space is defined as a continuous two-dimensional array with shape $(num_users, 4)$, where each row encodes the vector $[queue_length, SNR, deadline, time_since_last_scheduled]$ for an individual user. The action space is represented by a *MultiDiscrete* array of dimension num_rbs , where each element specifies the user index assigned to the corresponding RB.

The reward function is QoS-aware, meaning that each user's contribution to the total reward depends on their assigned service class. For *eMBB* users, the reward increases with high *SNR* and long *queue_length*; for *URLLC*, it prioritizes tight *deadlines* and good channel conditions; for *mMTC*, it favors shorter queues. After each action, the environment simulates system dynamics by depleting the queues of scheduled users,

TABLE I
ENVIRONMENT PARAMETERS AND TRAINING HYPER PARAMETERS

Parameter	Description / Range	Hyperparameter	Value
Number of users (<i>num_users</i>)	6 (default, configurable)	Learning rate	1e-3
Number of resource blocks (<i>num_rbs</i>)	3 (default, configurable)	GAMMA	0.99
Episode length (<i>max_steps</i>)	5 steps (default)	Replay buffer size	128
Queue length	Initialized $\sim U(0, 1)$, updated per step with $+N(0.05, 0.02)$	Batch size	8
SNR	Initialized $\sim U(0, 1)$, updated per step with $+N(0, 0.05)$	Sequence length	4
Deadline	Initialized $\sim U(0.3, 1.0)$, decreased by 0.1 if unscheduled	Epsilon start	1.0
Last scheduled	Reset to 0 when scheduled, +0.1 otherwise	Epsilon end	0.01
QoS types	Random assignment: eMBB, URLLC, mMTC	Epsilon decay	0.995

degrading deadlines for unscheduled users, and introducing random fluctuations in *queue_length* and *SNR*. Episodes terminate after a fixed number of steps (*max_steps*), enabling the RL agent to learn scheduling policies that balance fairness, urgency, and efficiency across diverse service classes.

Accordingly, the state space, action space, and reward function are as follows:

$$s_t \in [0, 1]^{\text{num_users} \times 4} \quad (1)$$

$$a_t = [u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{\text{num_rbs}}], \quad u_i \in \{0, 1, \dots, \text{num_users} - 1\} \quad (2)$$

where each u_i represents the user index assigned to the i -th resource block.

$$R(s_t, a_t) = \sum_{rb \in a_t} \text{QoS_reward}(rb) - 2 \cdot (\text{missed deadlines}) \quad (3)$$

with QoS-specific rewards depending on user type (*eMBB*, *URLLC*, *mMTC*). Table I presents the environment parameters.

We trained the agent for 5000 episodes with different combinations of hyperparameters. The most stable reward and loss results belonged to the runs as presented in Fig. 3.

We tested all three models and the best results belonged to the model trained using hyperparameters presented in Table I.

B. Results

We conducted a 200-episode test run on the trained model. Fig.4 (a) provides the details of the test results in terms of reward value and deadline violation rate of each episode in the test (regardless of the service type). This figure shows that the deadline violation rate is less than 0.2. Since some service types are more sensitive to deadline violations, in order to observe the results more constructively, Fig.4 (b) and Table II break down the test results for each service type. According to these breakdowns, the deadline violation varies between 0.32 % to 0.55 % with the best performance for eMBB and the worst for mMTC. However, all the values can be considered minimal and confirm the reliability of the agent.

TABLE II
QoS BREAKDOWN

Service	Average reward	Deadline violation
URLLC	1.271	0.50%
mMTC	1.295	0.55%
eMBB	0.950	0.32%

Fig. 3. Training plots

C. Addressed Issues and Open Challenges

This section begins by reviewing the challenges addressed by the proposed approach. By offloading all neural network-related computations, including inference, to the learner, the agents are freed from any model-specific overhead. This design choice ensures that increasing model complexity or size does not increase the computational demands on the agents; in fact, larger models may require fewer agents due to more efficient centralized processing. Additionally, batching inference on the learner and executing multiple environments per agent improves overall system utilization by maximizing accelerator usage (e.g., GPU/TPU) on the learner and CPU utilization on the agents. The number of cores dedicated to inference and training can be carefully tuned to balance workloads and minimize idle resources. Together, these design decisions significantly reduce the cost and inefficiency of RL experimentation, both at the edge and in the cloud.

Furthermore, all model-related operations are contained

Fig. 4. Test results. (a): Details of reward and deadline violation rate regardless of service type in 200 episodes test. (b): Reward and deadline violation rate percentage of each service type

within the learner, while only lightweight observation and action messages are exchanged between agents and the learner. This separation minimizes communication bandwidth requirements, making the architecture well-suited for deployment on resource-constrained edge sites or clouds.

Despite these advances, several open challenges remain for future research. The agent and learner must operate on separate physical devices, necessitating efficient, low-latency communication mechanisms. For instance, Google Remote Procedure Call (gRPC), a high-performance, open-source framework for remote communication in distributed systems, offers a promising solution for inter-device coordination [15]. Additionally, RL-based optimization problems often vary widely in nature, involving both discrete and continuous state/action spaces. Therefore, further research is needed to scale a broader range of RL algorithms into agent-learner architectures that can accommodate such diversity. Moreover, it is clear that a multi-agent distributed implementation is necessary to fully leverage the capabilities of the proposed scaled architecture.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we proposed a framework for RL workload placement in the cloud-edge continuum, enabling the scaling of RL agent processes across both domains. We demonstrated a prototype implementation of a scaled RL agent capable of performing QoS-aware resource block assignment and highlighted the open challenges associated with this approach. Considering these challenges, future research can further improve and extend the framework by deploying scaled agents across multiple virtual machines in multi-agent configurations and by leveraging diverse RL algorithms to address different optimization problems at the network edge.

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